

Paper 19

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF IDEAL ICE-CREAM

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ABSTRACT

Customer satisfaction helps the firms to understand the desired level of needs and wants of customers. Customer satisfaction is a tool used by the organisation to understand the effectiveness of their performance. Customer satisfaction refers to the power or ability to choose one thing over another with the anticipation that the choice will result in greater satisfaction or improved performance. The analysis of customer satisfaction helps the organisation to find out the weakness in their activities. The ideal ice-cream is an ice-cream manufacturing company based in mangaluru. It was started on 1st may 1975 by PrabhakarKamath and it is the biggest ice-cream manufacturer in mangaluru with an 80% market share. It has been serving the customers for more than 4 decades. It has currently four outlets in and around mangaluru, with one of its outlets in the market road is considered as India's largest ice cream parlour. In this research paper effort is applied to find out the satisfaction level of customers towards the ideal ice cream. The research is conducted on the basis of convenience method by taking 150 respondents opinion as a sample. The research is done by primary data collection; the primary data are collected with the help of online questionnaire.

Keywords: customer delight, literature review, objectives, data analysis and interpretation

1.Introduction:

S.Prabhakar Kamath, the founder of ideal ice-creams started out in business dealing in tailoring material and firecrackers. Seasonal fluctuations in those businesses got him thinking on a more secure line of business that would be in demand throughout the year. So, he decided to start an ice-cream parlour in spite of there being fierce competition in the segment. Setting out to make the best ice- cream possible, he taught himself the art of ice cream making and conducted experiments at home, testing his creations on enthusiastic neighbours. Three months later he launched ideal ice cream parlour on market road in Mangalore. On may 1, 1975 with 14 flavours. The rest is history. In two short years that he manufactured so tantalised the taste buds of Mangalorians that people were willing to wait in queue just to get

a chance to savor the ice-cream. Today ideal ice-cream has four parlours in Mangaluru city, one of which is the largest ice-cream parlour in the country[1].

Joined by his son Mukund kamath, the ideal brand has grown in leaps and bounds. Mukund has trained at the central food technology and research institute in Mysore and also the national dairy research institute of Bangalore. What's significant about ideal ice-cream is that it is 100% vegetarian. No egg is used Just pure fresh milk, cream and a secret formula that remains within the family[2].

2. Executive summary:

In this research paper effort is applied to find out the satisfaction level of customer towards ideal ice cream. The research is done by collecting primary data, with the research sample of 150 respondents. The primary data are collected with the help of questionnaire.

3. Literature review:

Customer satisfaction is the buzzword of marketing. According to jaspalsingh and gagandeep "customer satisfaction is the key to long term success of any company. It is influenced by the factors such as service innovation, reliability and accessibility and pricing and other facilities"[3]. According to kotler marketing is the process of profitably distributing customer satisfaction[4].

Customer satisfaction has been the subject of many studies since the early 1970s which have shown it to be a construct with reasonably good reliability that is distinct from related constructs such as customer attitudes, product performance and service quality.

Indian customers are visiting ice-cream parlours frequently, helping to fuel greater interest in packaged offerings in the country. The current ice-cream market of india is worth Rs.3000 cr, including the un organised sector.

5. Research methodology

To achieve our research objective, we carried out our research and collected information through convenience sampling technique. For this paper we have chose 150 samples in area of mangaluru. For the preparation both type of data are used i.e, both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through online questionnaire and secondary data were used only for collecting information regarding the ideal ice cream through journals, and internet.

6. Objectives

- 1 To know the satisfaction level of customers towards ideal ice cream.
- 2 To find out how the customer rank according to various characteristics of ideal ice cream.
- 3 To know influencing factor to buy ideal ice cream.
- 4 To know the customers opinion about ideal ice cream.
- 5 To know the effective media of advertising of ideal ice-cream.

7.Data analysis and interpretation

1. Which ice-cream you will prefer in ideal?

Interpretation

From the above graph we can conclude that, the majority of the respondents prefer dikush compared to other ice-creams.

2. Do you like to have fruits or without fruits in ice-cream?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that 111 respondent like to have with fruits ice cream, and about 39 like to have with fruits.

3. How did you come to know about ideal ice cream?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that majority of the respondent awareness is through friends and relatives other than advertisement and internet.

4. How many times you would visit ideal?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that 133 respondents visited ideal two or more time and 12 respondents visited only one and others had not visited.

5. Whether the delightness of ideal ice cream beyond your satisfaction?

Interpretation

On the basis of the satisfaction level 42 respondent conclude that delightness of ideal ice cream is best, 58 respondents as good 47 respondents as average, and others as poor.

6. Whether you will consider the price before buying the ice-cream?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that 48 respondents sometimes consider the price before buying ice-creams 27 respondents do not consider and 75 respondents consider the price of the ice cream.

7. What form of ice cream do you like?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that 9 respondents like candy, 35 respondents like cone, 34 respondents like slice, 54 respondents like family pack and remaining respondents like other forms of ice creams.

8. Which factor you will consider before buying ice cream brand?

Interpretation

From the above graph we conclude that the main factor considered by respondents are quality, product ingredients and flavours.

9. Please describe your few words about the ideal ice cream?

Interpretations

These are the ways the customers describe their feedback about ideal ice cream.

10. Are you satisfied with the services provided by the ideal ice cream?

Interpretation

From the above graph we can conclude that majority of the respondents are satisfied with the services of ideal ice cream. This shows that ideal ice cream is having a larger satisfied customer base.

8.Findings

On the careful observation of ideal ice cream, we have the following finding and suggestion:

- ✓ We collected information from age group of 18 to 40 years, we have observed that people of age group of 18 to 25 are maximum consumers of ideal ice cream.
- ✓ As per the data, 92 female and 58 male customers are satisfied with ideal ice cream.
- ✓ As per the data, 146 respondents are satisfied with the services of ideal ice cream.

Suggestion

They should increase in advertisement

9.Limitations

1. Some of the information provided by the respondents might not be correct
2. Getting timely responses from the respondents was the difficult task

10.Conclusion

The survey resulted in to the following conclusions:

1. Ideal ice cream must come up with the new promotional activities.
2. People are mostly satisfied with overall quality of ideal ice cream products.

Bibliography

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